

POLICY PAPER

Transit Without Policy: Tunisia's Struggle to Govern African Migration to Europe

Yasmine Jedidi

School of Economics, Administration and Public Policy, Doha Institute for Graduate Studies, Doha, Qatar

Correspondence: Yasmine Jedidi (yje001@dohainstitute.edu.qa; yasmine.aljedidi@gmail.com)

* The views and conclusions presented in this paper are solely those of the author and do not reflect the official position of any institution or organization.

June 2025

ABSTRACT

Recent shifting migration dynamics in North Africa have placed Tunisia at the center of transit routes for migrants from Sub-Saharan Africa heading to Europe, creating growing pressure on its economy, institutions, and international relations. This policy paper examines the main drivers of this trend, including regional instability, shifting migration routes, and the limited capacity of Tunisia's current migration policies. It reviews government actions such as return agreements, EU-funded border efforts, and enforcement measures, and highlights their shortcomings, particularly in terms of long-term planning and human rights protection. Drawing on examples from Morocco and Spain, the paper proposes a broader strategy that combines border control with legal pathways and stronger protection for migrants. The paper also discusses the role of international support and the practical challenges Tunisia may face in carrying out such a plan.

KEYWORDS Tunisia, Irregular Migration, Border control, Human rights, Migration Policy

Introduction

Tunisia, a small country in North Africa with roughly 12 million citizens (Tunisia Population (2025) - Population Stat, n.d.), has long been part of migration routes linking North Africa to Europe. For many years, the focus was on Tunisians leaving the country in search of better opportunities abroad, often through irregular means. In recent years, however, the country's role has shifted. It is now a major transit point for migrants from Sub-Saharan Africa trying to reach Europe, especially Italy (Meddeb & Louati, 2024). This shift has taken place without much planning or preparation, and it has created a difficult situation for both the Tunisian state and the migrants involved. Many migrants arrive through land borders with Algeria or Libya, stay briefly in coastal towns like Sfax or Zarzis, and then try to cross the Mediterranean in dangerous conditions. The number of people using Tunisia in this way has increased quickly and has drawn attention from European countries, especially Italy (Mohnblatt, 2024).

Several factors have contributed to this change. One of the main reasons is the tightening of migration routes through Libya, which used to be the most common route to Europe for many African migrants (MacGregor, 2019). After the 2017 agreement between Italy and Libya, which included European

support for migrant detention centers in the latter, reports of abuse, violence, and poor treatment pushed many people to avoid Libyan territory altogether. At the same time, ongoing crises in countries like Sudan, Guinea, and Niger have caused many people to leave their homes in search of safety or better economic opportunities. Tunisia, which has a long land border and an open coastline, has become one of their safest options.

The effects of this shift can be seen in many parts of Tunisian life. Towns near the coast, especially Sfax, have seen growing tensions between residents and groups of migrants. In early 2023, a speech by President Kais Saied blaming migrants for rising crime and social problems sparked a wave of arrests and violence (Cordall, 2023). Hundreds of Black migrants, including some legal residents, were detained or pushed toward the country's borders with Algeria and Libya. Human rights groups criticized the actions and raised concerns about the safety of those being expelled to desert areas with little support (Human Rights Watch, 2023). Internally, the issue of migration has become tied to wider problems, with increasing political instability, economic stress, and a lack of public trust in institutions.

At the same time, Tunisia is under pressure from the European Union to control migration. Financial aid from the EU is now linked to migration enforcement, and several agreements have been signed in recent years that include funding for border security (Sorgi, 2023). Critics argue that the Tunisian government is using migration as a bargaining tool in talks with European partners, offering to control migrant flows in exchange for loans or direct financial support. But even with this funding, the country's policies remain inconsistent. Some measures focus on stricter enforcement and arrests, while others allow flows to continue, depending on the political moment. What is missing is a clear and long-term plan that can guide its response in a way that protects both its national interests and the rights of migrants.

This policy paper looks at Tunisia's current position in the regional migration landscape. It reviews the main reasons behind the shift in migration patterns, assesses the steps taken by the Tunisian government so far, and compares these steps with approaches used in countries facing similar challenges, such as Morocco, Spain, and Greece. It then proposes a strategy that could help Tunisia manage migration more stably and fairly. Rather than focusing only on security or border control, the goal is to find a balanced approach that includes legal options, social protections, and stronger cooperation with international partners.

General Background

The rise in irregular migration through Tunisia cannot be understood without first considering the country's geographic position and its role within broader regional migration patterns. When analyzed, it can be understood that the migration trend is primarily driven by its geographic proximity to Italy. Pantelleria, an Italian island in the Sicily Channel, lies merely 60 kilometers from Tunisia's Cap Bon coastline (Annabi, 2017). Lampedusa, another critical destination, is only 130 kilometers away from the coastal zone between Sfax and Chebba, Mahdia governorates (Tasnim, 2023). Consequently, Italy has become the principal destination for migrants transiting through Tunisia. Most migrants from Sub-Saharan Africa arriving in the country regard it as a transit stop, with few intending long-term settlements, mainly due to the unwelcoming and "offensive" policies. World Bank data (2023) reveals that the migrant population in Tunisia was around 60,000 in 2020, marginally increasing to about 61,000 in 2023, still constituting less than 0.5% of the total population. This percentage is quite close to neighboring Morocco and Algeria, each with less than 1% migrant populations (International Migrant Stock, 2020).

Migrants from countries like Guinea, Cameroon, Sudan, and Niger often risk traversing one of the most dangerous migration routes in the world. In fact, since 2014, over 17,000 individuals have disappeared or died on this route (World Bank, 2023). Three primary departure areas have emerged: the northeast coastline (Bizerte to Nabeul/Cap Bon), close to Pantelleria Island; the east-central coast, including Sfax (Tunisia's economic hub, now a major transit point due to extensive smuggling networks, as seen in Figure 1), as well as the governorates of Mahdia, Monastir, and Sousse; and the southeastern coast stretching from Sfax governorate to the Libyan border.

Figure 1. African Migration from Tunisia to Europe

Source: Al Jazeera. (2024, September 10). Tunisia: The migration trap.

Despite the presence of some Middle Eastern migrants, as around 750 Syrians were observed between January and November 2023 (Frontex, 2023), the overwhelming majority are from Sub-Saharan Africa, primarily Côte d’Ivoire (Ivory Coast) and Guinea. The proportion of non-Tunisian migrants to Italy spiked from nearly 43% in 2022 to around 82% in 2023, significantly outnumbering Tunisians.

Figure 2. *Annual Arrivals to Italy from Tunisia (2018–2023)*

Source: Meddeb, H., & Louati, F. (2024, March 27). Tunisia’s transformation into a transit hub: Illegal migration and policy dilemmas. Malcolm H. Kerr Carnegie Middle East Center.

This dramatic increase is attributed to several factors first of which is political and economic instability, rising violence and insecurity, food insecurity in the Sahel region (UNHCR Global Focus, 2022), as well as the outbreak of civil wars and crises, such as the crisis in Sudan (Bonfiglio et al., 2023). Collectively, these dynamics have intensified refugee movements toward Europe. In addition, the 2017 Memorandum of Understanding between Italy and Libya, under which Libya received EU support to establish migrant detention centers, was widely criticized for human rights violations and inadequate food and health resources (Euro-Med Human Rights Monitor, 2023) and led many migrants to prefer Tunisia over Libya. Another contributing factor is the significant influx of migrants from Algeria since 2020, following economic deterioration and reduced job opportunities due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Many of these migrants expressed in interviews their intention to work in Tunisia temporarily before attempting to reach Europe (Tasnim, 2023).

Furthermore, African residents, including students and workers who have lived in Tunisia for several years under challenging circumstances, have faced racism, violence, and employment difficulties due to residency and work permit complications. They also struggle with limited access to essential services like healthcare and education, and severe penalties amounting to 3,000 Tunisian dinars (approximately 1,000 USD) for overstaying their visa by three months (El Ghali & Chemlali, 2022). Additionally, Tunisian President Kais Saied’s statements on February 21, 2023, sharply criticized by human rights groups and several countries, described “hordes of irregular migrants from Sub-Saharan Africa who came to Tunisia, accompanied by violence, crime, and unacceptable practices.” Following his remarks, hundreds of Africans faced violent attacks, and at least 840 Black migrants, including resident students and asylum seekers, were detained (Amnesty International, 2023). This was followed by reciprocal violence between Tunisians and migrants. It has been reported that security forces expelled over 5,500 migrants to the Libyan border, resulting in more than 100 deaths, and another 3,000 to the Algerian border (Dumont, 2023). These conditions pushed even legal residents to seek safer, more welcoming countries.

Policy Analysis

Current Policy Measures

In response to mounting migration pressures, the Tunisian government has adopted a range of reactive and often controversial measures. These have included mass expulsions of migrants to remote rural areas and border zones with Libya and Algeria. In addition, the government has signed bilateral agreements with countries such as Côte d'Ivoire and Mali to facilitate voluntary returns without penalties. However, the results have been minimal; for example, among 7,000 Ivorian migrants, 3,000 registered, yet only 1,053 (approximately 15%) actually returned (InfoMigrants, 2023), while migrant inflows continue rising. Tunisia has also entered into a financial agreement with the European Union that allocates 900 million euros through the IMF, including 115 million euros specifically aimed at tackling irregular migration (The Tahrir Institute for Middle East Policy, 2024). The government has been criticized for leveraging migration flows as political pressure on the European Union, most notably in September 2023, when migrant arrivals surged following the EU's rejection of President Kais Saied's demand to separate migration aid from the IMF funding agreement (Meddeb & Louati, 2024). Additionally, enforcement measures have been intensified, with arrests and heavy financial penalties targeting migrant smugglers and those organizing irregular migration.

Despite the breadth of these actions, the government's migration policies remain deeply inconsistent. At times, authorities strictly enforce coastal security and conduct raids against smugglers, while at other times, they appear to deliberately neglect such efforts. This hesitant enforcement has been seen as a tactical maneuver to pressure the European Union into increasing financial support. More fundamentally, the policies in place are largely repressive, failing to address the root causes of migration and often violating basic human rights. Mass expulsions, in particular, have placed thousands of migrants in life-threatening conditions in remote desert border regions.

Alternative Policy Options

While the current policy mix reflects Tunisia's urgent response to migratory pressures, it remains reactive, fragmented, and lacks a coherent long-term vision. The absence of an integrated strategy has not only undermined policy effectiveness but has also contributed to tensions on the ground, with violence against both resident and transiting African migrants. This has deepened social instability, particularly in coastal regions that serve as primary departure points. In light of these mounting challenges, it is essential to explore viable policy alternatives that Tunisia could adopt, drawing from international experiences and regionally relevant models. Policies of countries such as Morocco, Spain, and Greece, as well as frameworks proposed by the European Union, can offer valuable lessons to balance border management with migrant protection. We begin with Morocco, a regional counterpart that, like Tunisia, serves as a key transit point for Sub-Saharan migrants heading to Europe.

1- Morocco's Experience

We selected Morocco as our first alternative for several reasons. Firstly, both Morocco and Tunisia share a geographic location in North Africa, as well as cultural, social, and economic similarities. Secondly, both countries are situated near European coasts, making Morocco a destination for Sub-Saharan Africans on their way to Spain. Thirdly, Morocco also faces similar pressures from the European Union. As a response, it has strengthened its border surveillance, halted approximately 26,000 migration attempts, and dismantled 100 human trafficking networks in 2022 (European Commission, 2022). Additionally,

Morocco's policies are relatively more respectful of human rights, making it a place where migrants feel more comfortable settling (Welle, 2022). Morocco adopts a comprehensive and strategic approach to managing migration. Along with continuous border surveillance and efforts to disrupt migration attempts, authorities actively investigate and dismantle smuggling networks. Similar to Tunisia, voluntary return programs are coordinated through direct funding from the Interior Ministry in collaboration with migrants' countries of origin. Morocco has also ratified the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families, reinforcing its commitment to a human rights-based framework (Agence Marocaine de Presse, 2023).

A cornerstone of its approach is the National Migration and Asylum Strategy (International Relations Journal, 2023), which led to two major regularization campaigns in 2014 and 2016. These initiatives provided legal documentation for 50,000 migrants, particularly women and children, based on selective security criteria (Benjelloun, 2020), and were coupled with efforts to integrate migrants into Moroccan society through educational, cultural, and sports programs. The strategy also facilitated access to basic services such as healthcare, employment, and legal protection, while integrating migrant children into the public education system. To adapt to evolving needs, a dedicated committee was established to revise Law 02.03 governing the entry and residence of foreigners. Morocco's approach is further supported by robust cooperation with the European Union, including joint police investigations to control borders and combat smuggling networks (European Commission, 2022). EU financial assistance also supports Morocco's efforts to promote social and economic integration. In partnership with UNHCR, they offer training programs, free healthcare access, and material aid for vulnerable groups such as single women, children, and survivors of sexual violence (UNHCR, 2021)

2- Greece's Asylum System

Despite criticism of various Greek solutions, its asylum system has shown relative effectiveness. Implemented under International Protection Law 4636/2019, and effective since 2020, the system is composed of three entities: The Asylum Service, Appeals Authority, and Reception and Identification Service (Ministry of Migration & Asylum, 2023). Upon arrival, asylum seekers are registered and assessed to identify vulnerable groups, such as unaccompanied minors, pregnant women, elderly individuals, and victims of trafficking (Asylum Information Database, 2020). Registered applicants are issued an "international protection applicant" card that remains valid during the processing period. The procedure includes a personal interview, and the government provides free interpretation services to ensure accessibility. During the application process, individuals are granted access to essential public services such as healthcare and education, and eventually acquire the right to work. Those whose applications are approved receive a renewable three-year residence permit, along with government-provided accommodation.

3- Spain's Migration Policy

Spain's approach focuses on cooperation with migrant-sending and transit countries and could provide a model for Tunisia to manage migration and strengthen its regional cooperation. To address increased migration from Gambia and Mauritania, Spain introduced agreements of circular migration as an alternative to irregular migration. Through these agreements, the government issues temporary work visas to meet its annual labor demand, estimated at 250,000 workers, while offering migrants a legal alternative to dangerous routes, thus benefiting both Spain and migrant-sending countries economically through remittances (Mellersh, 2024). Furthermore, Spain plans to regularize irregular migrants' status over three

years, introducing the "Second-Chance Arraigo" program, which eases residence renewal conditions for former residents (Spainresidency, 2024).

4- Strict Human Rights Violation Laws

These laws include penalties for discrimination and violence against migrants, and against employers hiring irregular migrants. The EU's anti-human trafficking regulations stipulate a minimum sentence of five years imprisonment for basic trafficking crimes and ten years for crimes involving vulnerable victims, life-threatening conditions, or organized criminal groups (EUR-Lex, n.d.).

5- International Convention on the Protection of Rights of Migrant Workers and Their Families

This convention was adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1990 and has been practiced since 2003. It has been ratified by neighboring countries facing similar challenges, including Morocco, Algeria, and Libya. Its provisions offer a broad framework of protections for migrant workers and their families (OHCHR, n.d.). It protects migrants from slavery and servitude, gives them the right to freedom of expression, religion, and education in accordance with their personal beliefs. The convention also upholds respect for family life, privacy, and the confidentiality of communications. It ensures protection of property and both physical and psychological integrity, as well as a full set of rights during detention. It prohibits the arbitrary confiscation of documents and individual deportation without legal grounds, and completely bans collective expulsions. It also gives Migrants the right to appeal deportation decisions and settle any legal or administrative matters before leaving. In addition, the convention guarantees equal access to healthcare, public education for children, and fair treatment in public service institutions.

Evaluation of Alternatives

To evaluate the proposed policy alternatives, we apply a set of criteria that assess both normative and practical dimensions:

1. Alignment with the public interest, and whether the policy upholds Tunisia's international commitments while serving its national priorities. This demand balancing the needs of the key stakeholders who are:
 - Government institutions; the legislative (Tunisian Parliament), executive (ministries and public agencies), and judiciary.
 - Civil society actors, local NGOs (e.g., the Tunisian Organisation Against Torture), and international human rights organizations (e.g., Human Rights Watch).
 - Migrants and asylum seekers directly affected by migration policies.
 - International partners, including the European Union and UN agencies like UNHCR, operating in Tunisia.
 - Local communities, particularly in high-migration zones.
 - The private sector, especially industries facing labor shortages such as agriculture, construction, and tourism.
2. Policy effectiveness, focusing on the feasibility of implementation, required resources, and the current fiscal and administrative capacity.
3. The policy's potential to impact root causes and address structural drivers of irregular migration rather than merely its symptoms.

4. Justice and rights protection, equitable treatment of migrants, and compliance with human rights standards.
5. Balance of short- and long-term outcomes

Morocco's approach of intensified border surveillance, in cooperation with the European Union, alleviates national security concerns and reassures the public. It directly controls migration flows and, if properly implemented, ensures fairness. However, violations, which currently occur in Tunisia, lead to human rights abuses. This strategy may also lack long-term effectiveness and is costly, both financially and in terms of human resources, which Tunisia cannot sustain without external assistance. On the other hand, regularizing the legal status of migrants currently residing in Tunisia balances almost all stakeholder interests. Authorities would be responsible for defining and implementing procedures, though this approach might face public opposition and concerns. Migrants would gain legal status and improved living conditions, generating more tax revenues without significant governmental costs. Over the long term, this policy and its conditions can be adjusted based on migrant numbers, thus avoiding excessive strain on the system.

Implementing a formal asylum system similar to Greece's, especially given the absence of a Tunisian asylum law and reliance on UNHCR, will most likely face strong opposition from stakeholders, especially compared to regularization programs. Although it can be effective at addressing root refugee issues, establishing an official asylum system demands significant investment beyond the country's current resources. Even with international financial aid, implementation would be lengthy. While it could address long-term goals like refugee protection, it fails to solve short-term challenges and remains an extremely costly investment relative to current capabilities. The circular migration solution, on the other hand, aligns with Tunisia's long-term interests. It enables cooperation with Sub-Saharan African countries to formalize migration through temporary work visas; it would gradually reduce illegal migration flows and safeguard migrant rights. It would also benefit labor-shortage sectors like agriculture, construction, traditional industries (Al Jazeera, 2012), and tourism (Al Arabiya, 2023). Financially, this requires investment that could be partially supported through international funding from the EU and global partners.

Adopting strict laws against human rights violations achieves a public-interest balance by protecting migrants from verbal, physical, and exploitative abuses. It meets stakeholder expectations and immediately safeguards migrant dignity, aligning with principles of justice. This solution is cost-effective and achieves short- and long-term balance. Finally, while the International Convention on the Protection of Migrant Workers emphasizes justice and positively impacts migrants and families, it could be perceived as encouraging further migration. Given Tunisia's economic challenges, ratifying this convention will not be welcomed. Implementation also requires monitoring mechanisms and adjustments to national laws and institutions. In fact, migrant-hosting countries like the USA, Canada, Australia, and EU member states have not signed the convention due to its legal, political, social, and economic complexities. Nevertheless, aligning national practices with international standards may strengthen Tunisia's relations with migrant-sending countries and international organizations over the long term.

Recommended Policy

After a thorough assessment, we propose launching a comprehensive national migration strategy in partnership with the European Union and international organizations. This strategy should rest on five key pillars that address both immediate needs and long-term structural issues. First, border security must

be strengthened, with a focus on critical regions like Sfax and Nabeul, through proactive investigations into smuggling networks. These efforts should be supported by integrated EU oversight and have measures in place to ensure accountability and prevent potential security abuses. Second, the government should initiate a regularization program for migrants who meet clearly defined criteria, following thorough criminal background checks. This would better social integration and ensure their access to essential services such as healthcare and education. The government should also introduce circular migration programs based on temporary employment contracts. These programs can economically benefit both the country and migrants, without creating long-term demographic pressures. Additionally, robust legislation must be developed to address human rights abuses, with penalties reaching up to ten years of imprisonment. Such laws would demonstrate Tunisia's commitment to international standards and help protect migrants from exploitation. Finally, existing migration laws should be reformed to reflect the current realities and migration dynamics, equipping Tunisia's legal framework to respond to the evolving challenges of irregular migration.

Implementation Approach

Due to Tunisia's limited domestic resources, implementing this strategy will rely on robust international support, particularly from the European Union, with a balanced respect to both migrants and the country's interests. Strengthening border control will require advanced technology (such as drones and integrated surveillance systems) and specialized personnel training, resources that Tunisia cannot fully provide on its own. Therefore, financial and technical assistance from partners like the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and EU member states is critical to support border management capacity. With such support in place, the plan would aim to achieve extensive, near-full border surveillance coverage within a period of 18 months and to disrupt smuggling networks within two years. A real-world example of this working well is Morocco. With strong support from the EU, the country stopped over 26,000 people from leaving irregularly and broke up about 100 trafficking groups in just the first half of 2022.

In parallel, the strategy calls for a legal regularization program to grant long-term migrants a stable status. This would demand establishing a national committee to transparently vet applications for residency, using clear criteria, such as duration of stay and criminal background checks; it would also require digital platforms to streamline the processing. Technical support from the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) could help ensure the process meets international standards and human-rights norms. A realistic target is to formalize the status of roughly half of the currently irregular migrant population within three years, thereby improving their access to essential public services. Morocco also showed what's possible through its efforts in 2014 and 2016, when around 50,000 migrants were granted legal status. Spain is taking a similar path, rolling out a long-term plan to gradually bring undocumented migrants into the legal system.

As another component, the government should establish a circular migration initiative in partnership with the International Labour Organization (ILO) and interested African countries. Bilateral agreements can be negotiated to allow migrants from partner countries to work in Tunisia on a temporary, rotating basis, thus helping to fill labor shortages in certain industries while providing these workers with legal employment and skill-development opportunities. The plan would aim to finalize initial agreements within one year and, by the third year, have a substantial share of migrant labor needs being met through these regulated circular migration programs. Spain, for example, has made good use of circular migration deals with countries like Mauritania and Gambia, bringing in around 250,000 seasonal workers each year.

These programs have proven to be a win-win, as they help meet labor needs, support economic ties with partner countries, and lower the need to migrate illegally.

It is also important to make sure migrants are legally protected from discrimination and abuse. The parliament should pass and enforce more serious laws that punish racism, violence, and exploitation, in line with basic human rights. An independent national group could also be set up to look into reports of abuse and hold people accountable. On top of that, working with international human rights groups like Amnesty International and running public awareness campaigns across the country would help build a more tolerant society and cut down on abuse over the next years.

Potential Implementation Obstacles

While the proposed strategy offers a realistic and balanced approach to managing migration, several problems may come up during implementation. One key issue is the limited financial resources. Tunisia's current economic situation may delay or reduce planned investments in border equipment, legal systems, and public services. Getting timely and enough support from international partners will be necessary to move forward. Institutional capacity is another area of concern. The rollout of legal regularization programs and circular migration efforts will require strong coordination, trained staff, and reliable digital tools, none of which are fully in place today. Thus, better cooperation between national institutions and international agencies such as the IOM, UNHCR, and ILO will be needed.

Political and social resistance may also slow progress. Some parts of the strategy, like giving legal status to migrants or passing new anti-discrimination laws, may face pushback from parts of the public or political actors. The public debate around migration is already tense, and without clear and widespread communication, key steps may be stalled or watered down. Eventually, the long-term success of the strategy also depends on regular follow-ups and clear responsibilities. Without proper oversight and reporting, efforts may lose focus or fall apart over time. To avoid this, the government and its partners must make sure the work is open to input. Another critical point to mention is that Tunisia has become relatively isolated on the international stage after President Saied was widely criticized for concentrating power, especially following his suspension of parliament in 2021 (CNN Arabic, 2022). This shift has strained relations with the U.S. and the EU, leading to the freezing or withdrawal of several aid packages due to concerns over democratic backsliding (Foreign Policy, 2023).

Conclusion

Tunisia stands at a turning point. The growing movement of migrants through its territory has created urgent economic, social, and legal pressures. For too long, the government's actions have been short-term, reactive, and often harmful. This paper has shown that Tunisia needs a new direction, with cooperation, clear planning, and respect for human rights. The proposed strategy offers a realistic path forward. By combining stronger border control, fair legal regularization, circular migration, updated laws, and protection against abuse, Tunisia can manage migration in a way that serves both its people and those passing through. These efforts must be supported by long-term partnerships, especially with the European Union and international organizations, to help fill the gaps in funding, training, and tools. Success will not come easily, especially with financial and political challenges. But with clear goals and steady work, this strategy can reduce chaos, improve conditions on the ground, and help Tunisia move toward a more stable and fair approach to migration.

REFERENCES

- Al Jazeera. (2024, September 10). Tunisia: The migration trap. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2024/5/10/tunisia-the-migration-trap>
- Amnesty International. (2023, March 14). Tunisia: President's racist speech incites a wave of violence against Black Africans. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2023/03/tunisia-presidents-racist-speech-incites-a-wave-of-violence-against-black-africans/>
- Annabi, H. (2017). The illegal migration in the Mediterranean: the case of Tunisia. [www.academia.edu](https://www.academia.edu/90395240/The_Illegal_Migration_in_the_Mediterranean_The_Case_of_Tunisia). https://www.academia.edu/90395240/The_Illegal_Migration_in_the_Mediterranean_The_Case_of_Tunisia
- Asylum Information Database, European Council on Refugees and Exiles. (2020, October 13). Guarantees for vulnerable groups - Asylum Information Database | European Council on Refugees and Exiles. <https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/greece/asylum-procedure/guarantees-vulnerable-groups>
- Benjelloun, S. (2020). Morocco's new migration policy: between geostrategic interests and incomplete implementation. *The Journal of North African Studies*, 26(5), 875–892. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13629387.2020.1800207>
- Bonfiglio, A., Frouws, B., & Forin, R. (2023, May 4). Mixed migration consequences of Sudan's conflict. Mixed Migration Centre. <https://mixedmigration.org/mixed-migration-consequences-sudan-conflict/>
- Cordall, S. S. (2023, July 6). Africans attacked, flee Sfax, as Tunisia racial tensions explode. Al Jazeera. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2023/7/5/african-migrants-in-tunisia-face-discrimination-little-sympathy>
- Directive - 2011/36 - EN - EUR-LEX. (n.d.). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32011L0036>
- Dumont, J. (2023, October 5). "Ils nous ont dit de traverser la frontière, sinon ils nous tireraient dessus" : en Tunisie, une nouvelle vague d'expulsions de migrants vers l'Algérie. InfoMigrants. <https://www.infomigrants.net/fr/post/52358/ils-nous-ont-dit-de-traverser-la-frontiere-sinon-ils-nous-tireraient-dessus--en-tunisie-une-nouvelle-vague-dexpulsions-de-migrants-vers-lalgerie>
- El Ghali, A., & Chemlali, A. (2022). Ne rien faire et ne rien laisser faire. Les enjeux de la non-politique migratoire tunisienne. *Revue Tunisienne de Science Politique*, 7(1), 81-105. https://vbn.aau.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/468232034/Adnen_El_Ghali_and_Ahlam_Chemlali.pdf
- Euro-Med Human Rights Monitor. (2023, March 13). Italy-Libya Memorandum of Understanding: An affront to the fundamental human rights of migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers. <https://euromedmonitor.org/en/article/5561/Italy-Libya-Memorandum-of-Understanding:-An-affront-to-the-fundamental-human-rights-of-migrants,-refugees,-and-asylum-seekers>
- European Commission and Morocco launch renewed partnership on migration and tackling human smuggling networks. (2022, July 8). European Neighbourhood Policy and Enlargement Negotiations (DG NEAR). https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/news/european-commission-and-morocco-launch-renewed-partnership-migration-and-tackling-human-smuggling-2022-07-08_en
- Frontex. (2023). Annual Brief. <https://www.frontex.europa.eu/publications/annual-brief-2023-kIY45B>

- Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Migration & Asylum. (2023). Asylum Service. <https://migration.gov.gr/en/gas/>
- InfoMigrants (2023, March 24). Discours anti-Noirs du président Saïed : un nouveau vol de 290 Ivoiriens a quitté la Tunisie. <https://www.infomigrants.net/fr/post/47730/discours-antinoirs-du-president-saied--un-nouveau-vol-de-290-ivoiriens-a-quitte-la-tunisie>
- MacGregor, M. (2019, February 13). Changing journeys: Migrant routes to Europe. InfoMigrants. <https://www.infomigrants.net/en/post/15005/changing-journeys-migrant-routes-to-europe>
- Meddeb, H., & Louati, F. (2024, March 27). Tunisia's transformation into a transit hub: Illegal migration and policy dilemmas. Malcolm H. Kerr Carnegie Middle East Center. <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/03/tunisias-transformation-into-a-transit-hub-illegal-migration-and-policy-dilemmas>
- Mellersh, N. (2024, September 6). Spain's circular migration policy explained. InfoMigrants. <https://www.infomigrants.net/en/post/59661/spains-circular-migration-policy-explained>
- Mohnblatt, D. (2024, April 24). As African migration to Europe spikes, Tunisia takes center stage in Italy's foreign policy agenda - the media line. The Media Line. <https://themedialine.org/by-region/as-african-migration-to-europe-spikes-tunisia-takes-center-stage-in-italys-foreign-policy-agenda/>
- OHCHR. (n.d.). International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of all Migrant workers and members of their Families. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-convention-protection-rights-all-migrant-workers>
- Sorgi, G. (2023, September 22). Tunisia finally sees some migration money from EU despite backlash. POLITICO. <https://www.politico.eu/article/eu-tunisia-migration-funds-von-der-leyen-agreement/>
- Spainresidency. (2024, November 20). NEW SPANISH IMMIGRATION REGULATIONS. Residency in Spain Immigration, Visa, Golden Visa Spain, Spanish Immigration, Spanish Passport. <https://spainresidency.com/blogs/new-spanish-immigration-regulations/>
- Tasnim Abderrahim, "Tunisia: Increased Fragility Fuels Migration Surge," Global Initiative Against Transnational Organized Crime, July 2023, <https://globalinitiative.net/wpcontent/uploads/2023/06/Tasnim-Abderrahim-Tunisia-Increased-fragility-fuels-migration-surge-GI-TOC-July-2023.pdf>
- The Tahrir Institute for Middle East Policy (2024, September 6). The EU-Tunisia Memorandum of Understanding: a blueprint for cooperation on migration? <https://timep.org/2023/10/19/the-eu-tunisia-memorandum-of-understanding-a-blueprint-for-cooperation-on-migration/>
- Tunisia population (2025) - population stat. (n.d.). <https://populationstat.com/tunisia/>
- Tunisia: No safe haven for Black African migrants, refugees. (2023, July 19). Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/07/19/tunisia-no-safe-haven-black-african-migrants-refugees>
- UNHCR Global Focus.(2022). Sahel situation. <https://reporting.unhcr.org/operational/situations/sahel-situation>
- United Nations (2020). International Migrant Stock | Population Division. <https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/content/international-migrant-stock>

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. (2021, January). UNHCR Morocco fact sheet. <https://reporting.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/UNHCR%20Morocco%20fact%20sheet%20January%202021.pdf>

Volkman, E. (2023, January 13). Tunisia increasingly isolated under Saied as US loses interest. Al Jazeera. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2023/1/13/president-saied-isolating-tunisia-as-us-loses-interest>

World Bank. (2023). Tunisia Economic Monitor - Migration Amid a Challenging Economic Context (185650). Washington, D.C: World Bank Group. <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/099838011032326761/idu0b66401ea0d71b04eb00adb20a93d03ca730e>

ARABIC REFERENCES

Agence Marocaine de Presse, F. T. A. (2023, June 24). مكافحة الهجرة غير الشرعية : جهود المغرب بالأرقام. MAP. <https://www.mapnews.ma/ar/actualites/-المغرب-الشرعية-جهود-المغرب-سياسة/مكافحة-الهجرة-غير-الشرعية-في-مجال-مكافحة-الهجرة-غير-الشرعية#:~:text=بالأرقام>

CNN Arabic (2022, March 30). "رئيس تونس يحل البرلمان بعد لقاء افتراضي لأعضائه: "انقلاب فاشل". <https://arabic.cnn.com/middle-east/article/2022/03/30/tunisia-kais-saied>

CNN Arabic. (2023, May 21). رغم ارتفاع البطالة.. السياحة في تونس تعاني نقص اليد العاملة العربية. <https://www.alarabiya.net/aswaq/economy/2023/05/21/-تونس-تعاني-من-ارتفاع-نسبة-البطالة-السياحة-في-تونس-تعاني-من-نقص-في-اليد-العامة>

International Relations Journal. (2023, September 20). الهجرة غير الشرعية: النداءات الأمنية واستراتيجية المواجهة. <https://irajournal.academy/2023/08/07/illegal-immigration/>

Welle, D. (2022, February 6). لماذا أصبح المغرب وجهة استقرار لبعض المهاجرين الأفارقة؟ <https://www.dw.com/ar/لماذا-أصبح-المغرب-وجهة-استقرار-لمهاجرين-أفارقة/a-60590402>

معضلة في سوق العمل - الجزيرة. (2012). <https://www.aljazeera.net/videos/2012/10/4/-معضلة-في-سوق-العمل-بتونس>